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Advanced Film Industry 4.0 movie casting from Quantum Engineering Technology

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ABSTRACT

In modern latest technology there will be n number of bio-based quantum biotechnologies made into smooth-running video castings, so in these the sample of the human body at the microscopic level here eating flour is taken as the main chief content, and then the sample in the form of an atom from the human is taken, and then that will be injected into the idol or doll. These will be made to make movement in the lower or upper sky level; it may be the zenith or nadir side. These results in an earth-level species dancing act according to script or planned coding. On the planet Earth, only physical and AI means are present for capturing videos and editing them according to their taste. In all sky levels, all types of video movie casting will be made, but the process of operation is entirely different science and technology. The intention and aim target are the same, but the way is different. The movement of the idol or doll is obtained as a planned way of acting from the script, and then this movement is converted into the acting of a human person from the planet Earth. Sometimes the nail is sufficient for the attraction of some species on the planet Earth, including human beings. So, this entire one can analyze, and then you must visualize the concept of quantum engineering. The bathroom of any person's videos from planet Earth is taken into account for making a movie with AI-based earrings, so many are wearing clothes. The human body is the test body of all these activities to make a movie. So all these concepts are from all sky-level casting movies.

Keywords:-*Zenith, Nadir, upper sky, lower sky, load, physiology, space technology, movement, quantum engineering, idol.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Quantum engineering, in short, is called the conversion of the macroscopic level of the mechanics of materials subject to the microscopic level. The content of beams, bars, trusses, and frames in the MOM subject is converted to microscopic atoms and elements. These can be made by moving the idol (flour material) into movement, acting as made accordingly. The flour is made for pouring and blended in water and will be injected into the atom from whom that person was made into an enchantment; he is the main actor or artist. The whole entire movie is made into so many videos as from the movement of the idol or doll. The movement is overall from all 3 axes. X, y, and z properly. Then this is directly relative to the one man from the planet Earth.

The video quality is also pure; this is the biological way of the quantum biotechnology method of capturing and making video casting. Another method of casting video from other skies is that from any human body, a test body is made, and capturing bathroom video is taken for different cloth wearing as AI, and then movies from movement are made according to instructions.

2. QUANTUM ENGINEERING VIDEO IS HELPFUL FOR WORLD KING

If a person knows hitting technology sense level by taking input as images, then the protection is given to the king from the polar person you may think of as a super body. He can tolerate male or female or positive species energy or negative species energy images and give the main content of videos of the king wherever he goes. All video content is that from the polar super person only. [1-15]

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Yes, from 1 GPS to another GPS, capturing video and movie casting and loading signal and forcing signal can be

done easily. All these are done from quantum engineering.

4. CONCLUSION

- The sample in the form of an atom from the human is taken, and then that will be injected into the idol or doll.
- Quantum engineering, in short, is called the conversion of the macroscopic level of the mechanics of materials subject to the microscopic level. The content of beams, bars, trusses, and frames in the MOM subject is converted to microscopic atoms and elements.
- The movement is overall from all 3 axes. X, y, and z properly. Then this is directly relative to the one man from the planet Earth.
- If a person knows hitting technology sense level by taking input as images, then the protection is given to the king from the polar person you may think of as a super body
- Another method of casting video from other skies is that from any human body, a test body is made, and capturing bathroom video is taken for different cloth wearing as AI, and then movies from movement are made according to instructions
- Yes, from 1 GPS to another GPS, capturing video and movie casting and loading signal and forcing signal can be done easily. All these are done from quantum engineering.[16-27]

REFERENCES

1. Sunte, J. A Re view on Positive Semi Definite System on Vibration. *IJSRMME*, 6(3).
2. Sunte, J. An Elastohydrodynamic Lubrication of Synovial Lubricant on Human Body. *IJSRMME*, 6(3).
3. Sunte, J. A Review on 4D - Printing Design Materials. *IJSRMME*, 6(3).

4. Sunte, J. The Fracture Mechanics in Engineering Materials. *IJSRMME*, 6(3).
5. Sunte, J. The Municipal Plastic Waste Degradation Techniques. *IJSRMME*, 6(4).
6. Sunte, J. The Copper Materials Packing for Alignment Work in Dryers for Bearings in Paper Mill. *IJSRMME*, 6(4).
7. Sunte, J. The Design of 1 MW Solar Power Plant. *IJSRMME*, 6(4).
8. Sunte, J. The Survey of Renewable Energy Sources. *IJSRMME*, 6(4).
9. Sunte, J. Pacemaker Solutions to Heart Rhythm. *IJSRMME*, 6(4).
10. Sunte, J. The Material Failure by Von-Mise's Stress and Resonance Concept. *IJSRMME*, 6(4).
11. Sunte, J. Design of Floor and Stair Case Stone for Solution to Slip and Fall Accident. *IJSRMME*, 6(6).
12. Sunte, J. The Complete Problem-Solving Method of Viral Like Corona Waves from Root Level. *IJSRMME*, 7(1).
13. Sunte, J. Universal CG Role in National and International Level Prediction. *IJSRMME*, 7(1).
14. Sunte, J. Role of Photon on Biological Composite Hair for Some Videos Delivering. *IJSRMME*, 7(1).
15. Sunte, J. LING Pooja and BHOOMI Pooja in the Universe. *IJSRMME*, 7(1).
16. Sunte, J. The Controlling Measures and Solution to Problems of Earthquake. *IJSRMME*, 7(1).
17. Sunte, J. The Views, Likes, Share, Downloads, Ratings of Social Media Network. *IJSRCSEIT*, 8(4).
18. Sunte, J. The Problems and Solutions Regarding RF in Absence of Working Internet. *IJSRCSEIT*, 9(1).
19. Sunte, J. A Reversible Elastic, Plastic and Fracture Properties for Engineering Materials. 9(12).
20. Sunte, J. Importance of salts and sugars in practical life. *Advancement in Mechanical Engineering and Technology*, 6(1), 1–3.
21. Sunte, J. Importance of Carbon, hydrogen, oxygen Prakruti, Jala, Treatment on Human Body. *Research and Development in Machine Design*, 6(1).
22. Sunte, J., Sirsgi, S. (2023). Design of Barrier Stick for Protection of Human Beings. *Research and Development in Machine Design*, 6(1).
23. Sunte, J. (2023). The Fire Solution to Aeroplane Crashes, Failure Reasons for Human Life. *Research and Reviews: Journal of Mechanics and Machines*, 5(1).
24. Sunte, J. (2023). The Belly Fat Problem Solving Method and Analysis. *Research and Reviews: Journal of Mechanics and Machines*, 5(1).
25. Sunte, J. 2023. The new future trend of zero budget movie film making advancement of computer technology and its applications, 6(2).
26. Sunte, J. 2023, the balanced human body weight solution from underweight. *Journal of Trauma, Orthopedic and Urological Nursing*, 1(1).
27. Sunte, J. 2022. A Review on Design Considerations for Engineering Materials. *IJERT*10(11)